

Narrative of Lecturer Performance During Technology: Development of a Post-Pandemic Work System

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Abstract: The pandemic continues to decline, and things are starting to return to normal now, but not with the reality of lecturers' work in Indonesia. Work from home system has been in place for more than a year and make lecturers enjoy this flexibility work. Working from home for a long time, makes workers experience higher pressure than usual. Some workers even become unproductive and experience a decline in performance. Leaders have an important role in every organization. Leaders must take the right policies so as not to make the job more difficult. This research is exploratory quantitative research with a population of university lecturers. The sample used is 154 and uses a stratified random sampling technique. Data were taken by questionnaire and analysed by SEM analysis using warpPLS. This study found that leadership had no effect on lecturer performance, either as a moderating variable or as an independent variable. The system of working from home is influenced only by the circumstances of the individual himself and everything that comes to his mind. However, if the work from home system continues, leaders can be an important influence on lecturer performance. Developing a work system that keeps lecturers productive but not burdensome will be effective in supporting the performance of lecturers both in learning and non-learning.

Keywords: Stress, Work Motivation, Leadership, Lecturer Performance, Work From Home.

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Introduction

Since the outbreak of Covid-19 in Indonesia in 2020, the government immediately made a policy to limit the movement of people outside the home. As a result, many government and private offices have implemented work from home schemes. This scheme can be said to be part of the telecommuting concept which is not new in the world of work. Turkmenoğlu (2020) revealed that this system has been known since the 1970s which aims to overcome everyday traffic problems. However, this system is implemented normally and is not mandatory.

Bloom (2014) in his research states that working from home can increase a person's productivity because of the ease with which it is found. However, the understanding of working from home in Bloom (2014) is not only doing work at home but can be in other places such as libraries and others. This is reinforced by Eldridge's (2010) statement that working from home refers to an individual's flexibility to work anywhere other than the office. Meanwhile, during this pandemic, the meaning of working from home has become narrow. Doing no activity anywhere other than the office, but people are really being forced to work from home.

One of the advantages stated by Gorlick (2020) in this work from home system is that there is a balance between work and family life and individuals can control the work schedule and

work atmosphere as desired. Based on these advantages, the leadership feels that the performance of lecturers will be better if this system is applied compared to working in an office which tends to be inflexible. Because the lecturer work system can indeed be done anywhere. In fact, the performance of lecturers has decreased from the previous year (Jena, 2020; Purwanto, 2020). This performance drops for no reason, there are several factors that cause this to happen.

Psychological disorders occur mainly in individuals who are accustomed to a conventional office atmosphere and are still not accustomed to dividing work and family time at one time. Zaka (2020), in his research, stated that the performance of lecturers during this pandemic tends to decline due to the high level of stress experienced. Job stress is caused by high job demands and more work because they must look for innovation, especially in learning. According to Hoyt et al. (2021) that the performance of lecturers is indeed more qualified if they go directly to the field. Due to the existing limitations, lecturers must carry out the latest innovations to continue to carry out their duties properly. Therefore, high demands will make the work of lecturers pile up.

H1: Job stress affects lecturer performance.

Morrish (2019) states that lecturers' performance can improve if they have leaders who are able to protect and provide comfort and work security for them. When workers feel

comfortable and safe with a leader who is supervising them, they will create a sense of trust and will not object to the demands of the job given. Diran et al. (2020) added that currently elements of society need organizational leaders who can guide workers in dealing with times of crisis due to the pandemic, overcoming limitations and fears that arise in workers which have a negative impact on their performance.

The ideal leader for all circles is indeed difficult to find, but the basic need during a pandemic that is met by leaders is the high level of nurturing and understanding of many work indicators that their subordinates cannot achieve (Bartsch et al., 2020). Unfortunately, not all leaders understand the current crisis, job demands are still prioritized and make workers' performance even lower. According to Sultana (2020), the leader of an organization can be a cause of stress for an employee. An authoritarian leadership model will add to the burden on employees during a pandemic.

H2: Leadership can be a moderating variable of job stress on lecturer performance.

Motivation is the highest factor to spur lecturer performance in working and studying during this pandemic (Spurk, 2020). Currently the whole community prioritizes health so that it is not easily exposed to the virus. Moreover, in May 2021, the second wave of the Covid-19 pandemic began to arrive and the virus that was spreading was more vicious than before. The high motivation to avoid viruses and live healthy, exceeds the motivation of workers to improve performance during the pandemic (Mahmoud, 2020). Kooji (2020) explains that the low motivation of lecturers is caused by: (1) many lecturers who work only because of routine; (2) more waiting to be asked to do work; and (3) a lack of sense of belonging to the organization in which they live.

Motivation is the key to organizational success to keep the job strong and help the organization survive. Motivation is a need in individuals and helps achieve targets smoothly. According to Panisoara (2020) motivation is an evolution of behaviour that supports and encourages goal directed. Motivation becomes an inner strength that can encourage lecturers to do their jobs. Motivation is measured through existence needs, relationship needs, and growth needs. All those needs can initiate lecturers in improving lecturer performance.

The need to be seen by the leadership becomes a spur for lecturers to improve performance. This is more commonly found in organizations that have leaders with a method of seeing results. However, when this is applied during this pandemic, it certainly becomes unhealthy for individuals. Wang et al. (2021) stated that in China, many lecturers lose motivation at work due to lack of concentration when doing work from home. In addition, limited space makes lecturers lose their enthusiasm in conducting research, service or teaching. As a result, in 2020, the performance of lecturers decreased drastically compared to the previous year.

H3: Job motivation affects lecturer performance.

Leaders can mediate in increasing the motivation of lecturers to boost their performance. Relationship needs in measuring motivation, can be seen horizontally and vertically. The horizontal relationship describes the relationship between lecturers, while the vertical relationship shows the relationship between

lecturers and leaders. During this pandemic, the relationship between the two must run better than usual. Relationship needs that are met can increase a lecturer's sense of belonging to his organization and a greater sense of responsibility towards his work. According to Wilson (2021), vertical relationships that continue to exist without any demands can make lecturers feel valued and embraced personally. This feeling becomes a motivation for lecturers to continue their work without feeling that working from home is a burden.

H4: Leadership can moderate the effect of work motivation on lecturer performance.

The pandemic period that has passed for one year has made all aspects of life have a new period called the new normal. This new normal will also be implemented in the teaching and working system of lecturers. The work system in this new normal era will not be the same as before the pandemic. Many things have been changed and adapted to the new way of working. This new normal change must also be able to include technological revolutions that continue to develop from time to time so that organizations are ready to change at any time (Carroll and Conboy, 2020; Bartsch et al., 2020). One element that must be changed is the way of leadership. Facing the new normal and changes due to the technological revolution requires its own tricks so that lecturer performance does not continue to decline (Risley, 2020). Moreover, working from home makes good relations between lecturers and leaders tenuous.

H5: Leadership influences lecturer performance.

Research Methods

This study used an exploratory quantitative approach with the aim of deepening knowledge and seeking new ideas in the symptoms of certain phenomena as well as explaining the occurrence of events in the study. This research was conducted at the Faculty of Economics ex-Institution for Educational Personnel throughout Indonesia. Sampling is done in stages. The first and second samples technique were taken to determine the islands and provinces to be taken using the area probability sampling technique. The island of Java and especially Central Java, was chosen as the sample because Central Java has the highest number of ex-Institutions for Educational Personnel Education. The election resulted in lecturers from Semarang State University and Sebelas Maret State University. The number of known populations is 250. From that population, a sample is taken using the Slovin formula with a standard error of 5% and 154 lecturers are obtained to be used as samples and taken by stratified random sampling. The data collection technique used is a closed questionnaire which will be analysed using a structure equation model using the WarpPLS analysis tool.

Result

Outer Model

The evaluation of the outer model is carried out to construct each indicator from the existing variables to find out whether there are errors that occur. This evaluation includes the assessment of convergent validity and composite reliability. The construction of indicator values can be seen from the combined value of loading and cross loading. The accepted outer model is indicated by the loading factor value of each indicator or question from each variable must be > 0.70 . The results of this research

model indicate that there are still several indicators of all variables whose values are < 0.70. The indicator must be omitted if the AVE value of each variable is < 0.50.

Based on the above analysis, indicators that do not meet the construct requirements will be eliminated so that the research model is not damaged by several indicators that can bias the data.

Table 1.1. Loading Factor P Value, AVE, Composite Reliability

Item	Loading Factors	P-Values	AVE	Composite Reliability
Stress				
X1.1	0,802	<0,001	0,525	0,923
X1.2	0,685	<0,001		
X1.6	0,703	<0,001		
X1.7	0,759	<0,001		
X1.8	0,752	<0,001		
X1.9	0,743	<0,001		
X1.10	0,581	<0,001		
X1.11	0,808	<0,001		
X1.12	0,781	<0,001		
X1.13	0,684	<0,001		
X1.14	0,635	<0,001		
Motivation				
X2.1	0,739	<0,001	0,550	0,944
X2.2	0,708	<0,001		
X2.3	0,771	<0,001		
X2.4	0,828	<0,001		
X2.5	0,655	<0,001		
X2.6	0,618	<0,001		
X2.7	0,607	<0,001		
X2.8	0,770	<0,001		
X2.9	0,871	<0,001		
X2.10	0,809	<0,001		
X2.11	0,873	<0,001		
X2.12	0,756	<0,001		
X2.13	0,772	<0,001		
X2.14	0,508	<0,001		
Leadership				
M3.3	0,795	<0,001	0,514	0,893
M3.4	0,524	<0,001		
M3.5	0,801	<0,001		
M3.6	0,741	<0,001		
M3.8	0,714	<0,001		
M3.9	0,787	<0,001		
M3.11	0,704	<0,001		
M3.12	0,622	<0,001		

Lecturer Performance				
Y1.2	0,565	<0,001	0,500	0,899
Y1.3	0,786	<0,001		
Y1.4	0,722	<0,001		
Y1.6	0,708	<0,001		
Y1.9	0,675	<0,001		
Y1.10	0,786	<0,001		
Y1.11	0,790	<0,001		
Y1.12	0,625	<0,001		
Y1.13	0,675	<0,001		

Source: data process 2023

The research model can be accepted if it meets convergent validity and composite reliability. The convergent validity model is seen from the loading factor value for each indicator and the AVE for each variable, while composite reliability is seen from the composite reliability coefficient for composite reliability where the condition is that the composite reliability value > 0.70 then the questionnaire is declared reliable.

The table above shows the composite reliability coefficient values for all variables. All variables in this study with a sample of social studies lecturers have met composite reliability with the condition that the composite reliability coefficient value > 0.70 has been met by all variables. Thus, the outer model of this research with a sample of social studies lecturers can be accepted without changing the indicators.

Table 1.2. Correlations among Latent Variables and errors

	Stress	Motivation	Leadership	Performance
Stress	0,724	0,076	0,027	-0,293
Motivation	0,076	0,742	0,420	0,363
Leadership	0,027	0,420	0,717	0,579
Performance	-0,293	0,363	0,579	0,707

Source: data process 2023

Based on the table above, there is a correlation between all variables in their diagonal values. All variables have a good correlation with other variables. It can be described that all variables meet the criteria of discriminant validity. So, based on the test results of convergent validity, composite reliability, and discriminant validity, this research model with a sample of social studies lecturers can be accepted so that the inner model can be analyzed further.

In the WarpPLS analysis, there are several measures of model fit and quality indices that must be met. The following are the results of the fit and quality index model in this study:

Table 1.3. Model Fit dan Quality Indices

No	Model Fit dan Quality Indices	Fit Criteria	Result	Ref
1	APC	$p < 0,05$	0,344 $p < 0,001$	Accepted
2	ARS	$p < 0,05$	0,356 $p < 0,01$	Not Accepted
3	AARS	$p < 0,05$	0,344 $p < 0,01$	Accepted
4	AVIF	<i>Acceptable if ≤ 5, ideally $\leq 3,3$</i>	1,053	Ideal
5	AFVIF	<i>Acceptable if ≤ 5, ideally $\leq 3,3$</i>	1,502	Ideal
6	GoF	<i>Small $\geq 0,1$, medium $\geq 0,25$, large $\geq 0,36$</i>	0,431	Big
7	SPR	<i>Acceptable if $\geq 0,7$, ideally = 1</i>	0,800	Accepted
8	RSCR	<i>Acceptable if $\geq 0,9$, ideally = 1</i>	0,965	Accepted
9	SSR	<i>Acceptable if $\geq 0,7$</i>	1,000	Accepted
10	NLBCDR	<i>Acceptable if $\geq 0,7$</i>	0,700	Accepted

Source: data process 2023

The table above shows that overall, the results of the fit model and the sample quality index of the research model have met the criteria that must be met. This research can be continued to the hypothesis testing stage.

Hypothesis test

Model testing will be seen from the results and model values that come out in the SEM analysis that has been carried out. The test criteria for this model are the same as for the fit and quality index model discussed above. The purpose of testing this model is to see the direction, relationship, and magnitude of the coefficients between variables.

Picture 1.1. Research Model

The test data from the above model is presented in the form of a table below:

Table 1.4. Research Model Results

No	Path	Coefficient	P Value
1.	Job stress affects lecturer performance	0,36	< 0,001
2.	Motivation influences lecturer performance	0,26	<0,001
3.	Leadership moderates the effect of job stress on lecturer performance	0,15	0,049
4.	Leadership moderates the influence of motivation on lecturer performance	0,43	<0,001
5.	Leadership affects lecturer performance	0,53	<0,001

Source: data process 2023

Discussion

Job Stress Affects Lecturer Performance

The results showed that work stress on lecturer performance had a positive direction with a coefficient value of 0.36 and p value <0.001. These results indicate that this study accepts H1 which reads that there is an effect of work stress on lecturer performance, where this relationship indicates that when a lecturer's job stress increases, his performance will decrease. It was explained that stress is a condition that can affect two variables in an individual at once, namely physical, and psychological. Stress can trigger other physical ailments that affect a person's health. If stress has peaked and cannot be controlled anymore, it will have a real impact and affect the performance of a lecturer (Wang et al., 2021).

In their work obligations, lecturers have the basic works, namely teaching, research, and service. All aspects of work during the pandemic changed drastically without any prior preparation. Dima (2021) stated that it is easier for a lecturer to reach the point of saturation in his work due to the pandemic and the system of working from home. The work of lecturers is piling up, especially preparing for online learning is not as easy and flexible as preparing for offline learning. There are many obstacles that must be solved by a lecturer in various jobs. And unfortunately, these obstacles often cannot be resolved by themselves (Troughakos, 2020; Golightley and Holloway, 2020).

The work stress felt by lecturers in Indonesia is the result of a combination of piled up work, difficulty in concentration obtained due to the division of office work and homework that does not have clear boundaries, panic, and anxiety due to the

pandemic, and the boredom experienced still does not know when it will end. The results of this study are supported by the research of Sultana (2020) that in this time of crisis, people choose to think more about their health than anything else. However, this option is difficult to achieve for workers who are forced to work from home, this also applies to lecturers.

Research conducted in the UK also found that stress during the pandemic was more harmful than work stress during the pre-pandemic. Increased responsibilities and demands for innovation in education add to the workload, especially for lecturers who are married and have children. The performance of lecturers cannot be allowed to continue to decline in the present because it has a negative impact on the organization. The new normal era has also begun to be initiated and carefully planned to change the work habits of lecturers. The new normal work system is expected to be able to reduce the stress level of lecturers to a smaller number and can improve performance back to normal or even better.

Leadership Moderation on Job Stress and Lecturer Performance

The results showed that leadership can moderate work stress on lecturer performance, with a coefficient value of 0.15 and p value <0.0049. These results indicate that this study accepts H2 which reads leadership can moderate the effect of job stress on lecturer performance, where this relationship indicates that leadership can be an alternative to improve lecturer performance by reducing lecturer stress levels. However, in this study, the significance level of leadership moderation was very low. That is, 99% of the possibility of work stress cannot be reduced by means of better leadership than before.

In this pandemic period, lecturers need a leader who is a solution, who can overcome the limitations that have been a barrier and who together protect this crisis so that no pressure is felt by lecturers. Not many leaders are able to understand this critical situation and instead pressure lecturers to continue to innovate and change their fields and demand high performance. This aspect can be moderated by increasing lecturer's work stress which results in a decrease in lecturer performance.

This research was conducted during a pandemic that had passed more than a year. So far, many lecturers have not been able to adapt to changes, both changes in work systems and changes in emotional control. The role of the leader is needed in terms of changing the work system (Wong et al., 2021). The formulation of new policies and support that does not complicate the lecturer's work at home and does not have high expectations of the lecturer's work, can at least help reduce lecturer's work stress. Reducing work stress can trigger high performance.

Unfortunately, it only affects no more than 2% during this pandemic (Siswanti and Muafi, 2020). Because the work from home system ultimately minimizes meetings with the leadership, if the leadership cannot create a system that maintains close vertical relationships, the leadership factor still cannot provide a significant influence in minimizing lecturer work stress and improving lecturer performance.

The work stress experienced by lecturers in Indonesia comes from their own thoughts. Working from home is a new reform for lecturers in Indonesia who previously had to work

conventionally in the office and carry out research and direct service in the field. This drastic change and no other choice burdened all lecturers and caused boredom that was difficult to overcome. Moreover, the pandemic period, which is expected to end soon after the government begins to design a new normal era, will be further extended due to the increasing number of cases. Feelings of boredom, anxiety, fear, and pressure to innovate are the main stress factors in this study. All these factors arise from within each lecturer which are difficult to minimize by improving vertical relationships.

Motivation on Lecturer Performance

The results showed that work motivation on lecturer performance had a positive direction with a coefficient value of 0.26 and p value <0.001. These results indicate that this study accepts H3 which reads that there is an influence of work motivation on lecturer performance, where this relationship indicates that when a lecturer's work motivation increases, his performance will also increase.

Motivation is defined by Tang et al. (2020) is a psychological force in determining a person's direction, level of effort, and level of persistence. All lecturers have different motivations to want to work well to meet their needs. It can be said, the high and low motivation of a person depends on the level of need in the organization. Lecturers with a higher need for existence than others tend to have high work motivation. This motivation has a strong meaning on the performance of a lecturer.

The results of this study are supported by Sembiring et al. (2020) which states that someone with good performance and increasing from year to year can certainly have very high organizational needs. This need will stimulate individual motivation to work. In a work from home system, strong motivation is needed so that lecturers continue to get good performance. However, the system which was initially welcomed by the academic community in Indonesia, has gradually become a formidable scourge to survive. Some things in a lecturer's work would be better done in the field (Davidescu et al., 2020) because it demands intense communication and high face-to-face meetings. Limitations due to regulations to break the chain of the pandemic, forcing lecturers to carry out these activities from home which reduces their motivation.

According to University data, at the start of working from home, the average performance of lecturers increased by 13% from usual. This is due to the high motivation of lecturers to work from home and carry out various kinds of innovations with unlimited time. Working from home becomes more flexible because office and homework can be done simultaneously. However, after 10 months have passed, the performance of lecturers has decreased due to physical and mental fatigue and boredom which is increasingly difficult to treat. After the work from home system was implemented, lecturers also began to lose the need for their existence in the organization. Due to the loss of various needs, motivation also decreases which results in decreased performance during this pandemic.

Leadership Moderation on Lecturer Motivation and Performance

The results showed that work motivation on lecturer performance had a positive direction with a coefficient value of

0.43 and p value <0.001. These results indicate that this study accepts H4 which reads leadership can moderate the effect of work motivation on lecturer performance, where this relationship indicates that leadership can be an alternative to improve lecturer performance by increasing lecturer work motivation.

In the practice of leadership there is a dimension of exemplary and influence that is so dominant. Meetings or discussions that are often held by the leadership can generate motivation and strong belief for lecturers that this situation will soon pass and lecturers can work again with normal situations. In addition, the leadership believes that post-pandemic organizational performance will be better because there are many innovations and works by lecturers to survive in a work from home situation. Of course, this practice is not to pressure lecturers to continue working and improve their performance even during this pandemic.

Leadership practices that provide exemplary and compassion can make lecturers have the confidence and self-strength to know the direction to move with certainty (Risley, 2020). Leadership is a very strong moderating variable in increasing the influence of motivation on lecturer performance, because of the emergence of cause and effect (Wolor et al., 2020). Leaders of universities or faculty units who can carry out their roles by providing clear directions, have an effective leadership style, and are able to overcome limitations are believed to be able to encourage lecturers' motivation to work in the midst of limitations so as to improve their performance.

Leadership on Lecturer Performance

The results showed that leadership on lecturer performance had a positive direction with a coefficient value of 0.53 and p value <0.001. These results indicate that this study accepts H5 which reads that there is an influence of leadership on lecturer performance, where this relationship indicates that when the leader applies an effective and nurturing style, the lecturer's performance will tend to increase.

There are several kinds of leadership styles according to theory, all these leadership styles tend to refer to normal conditions (Netolicky, 2020). This pandemic period is also called the crisis period because all levels of society experience anxiety even though they have different forms of anxiety. Today, an employee not only needs a capable leader, but also needs a leader who can understand this crisis so as not to impose the will of the organization's goals on workers and pressure them to continue working.

A leadership style that can provide solutions and open limitations for lecturers is more needed to improve performance in this pandemic era (Chen et al., 2020). This study succeeded in answering the research limitations of Hlubocky et al., (2021) which stated that leadership has a negative effect on lecturer performance, meaning that the figure of a leader can reduce lecturer performance. Another factor that can be answered by this research is the willingness of the leadership to understand the situation and the willingness to provide a sense of security from the situation will improve the performance of lecturers during the pandemic.

Over time, this leadership style can be applied in welcoming work in the new normal era. Where when things start to return to normal but still have to apply health protocols in their activities. Leaders who can pay special attention to performance

development programs are better able to make lecturers better at work and can improve their performance.

Conclusion

Work stress and work motivation have a significant effect on lecturer performance. These two variables are factors that arise because of a work from home system that has never been experienced before. High stress and a decrease in work motivation due to boredom felt for more than one year working from home with limitations, can reduce the performance of lecturers in general. Leadership also has a strong influence on lecturer performance. So that the old, authoritarian, and demanding leadership style will reduce the performance of lecturers. Leaders who understand the crisis period of this pandemic era and can overcome limitations to prepare for the new normal that is able to boost the performance of lecturers. The influence of leadership is very small in moderating stress levels and lecturer performance. Under normal conditions, the leader factor can help reduce the work stress of the lecturer, but during this pandemic, 98% of the stress factor arises from within the individual lecturer himself. So that the leader does not have a big role in controlling the emotions of the lecturer. The update in this research can be seen from the emergence of the leadership style that lecturers want during the pandemic, so that it triggers them to get superior performance. In addition, work stress that comes because of one's own thinking, so that special solutions are needed to overcome work stress due to work from home so that the performance of lecturers can increase again.

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